

HYPERHOMOCYSTEINEMIA AND RISK FACTORS, ITS SYMPTOMS IN BODY

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Annotation

Homocysteine is an amino acid that the body produces. Most people have low homocysteine levels. This is because the body breaks down the amino acid quickly into other compounds. High, or elevated, homocysteine levels are known as hyperhomocysteinemia. This could indicate a person has a vitamin deficiency, as the body needs certain nutrients to break it down. Less commonly, hyperhomocysteinemia can occur due to homocystinuria, which is a genetic disease. Homocystinuria means that the body is not able to process the building blocks of amino acids properly.

Key words: hyperhomocysteinemia, homocystinuria, thromboembolic diseases, thrombosis, vitamin deficiency,

High plasma levels of homocysteine are the results of the interplay between congenital and environmental factors. In the last two decades, a growing amount of interest has focused on mild-to-moderate Homocysteine is an amino acid that the body produces. Most people have low homocysteine levels. This is because the body breaks down the amino acid quickly into other compounds. High, or elevated, homocysteine levels are known as hyperhomocysteinemia. This could indicate a person has a vitamin deficiency, as the body needs certain nutrients to break it down. Less commonly, hyperhomocysteinemia can occur due to homocystinuria, which is a genetic disease. Homocystinuria means that the body is not able to process the building blocks of amino acids properly as a risk factor of thromboembolic diseases. Case-control and cross-sectional studies clearly indicated that mild-to-moderate hyperhomocysteinemia is associated with heightened risk of both arterial and venous thrombosis. On the other hand, prospective studies did not unequivocally show that hyperhomocysteinemia is associated with a high thrombotic risk. Therefore, additional studies are needed to define whether hyperhomocysteinemia is a risk factor for thrombosis, especially of the venous circulation. Among these, prospective cohort studies will clarify better the temporal relationship between high homocysteine levels and the thrombotic event. Most importantly, however, randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind

trials of the effects of homocysteine-lowering vitamins on the thrombotic risk are urgently needed. Not only will they help in defining whether the relationship between hyperhomocysteinemia and thrombosis is causal, they will also have a potential dramatic impact in the prevention of thromboembolic events.

Homocysteine is an amino acid produced when proteins are broken down. High homocysteine levels usually indicate a deficiency in vitamin B-12 or folate.

A normal level of homocysteine in the blood is less than 15 micromoles per liter (mcmol/L) of blood.

Higher levels of homocysteine are split into three main categories:

Moderate: 15-30 mcmol/L

Intermediate: 30-100 mcmol/L

Severe: greater than 100 mcmol/L

Hyperhomocysteinemia itself usually does not cause any symptoms in adults, though it can in children. Symptoms can also vary from one person to the next and be subtle.

Doctors may order a homocysteine test if they suspect you have a vitamin deficiency, and if you begin exhibiting symptoms of a vitamin deficiency.

Symptoms of a vitamin B-12 deficiency include:

- pale skin
- weakness
- fatigue
- tingling sensations (like pins and needles) in the hands, arms, legs, or feet
- dizziness
- mouth sores
- mood changes

Symptoms of a folate deficiency are often subtle and are similar to those of a B-12 deficiency. These include:

- fatigue
- mouth sores
- tongue swelling
- growth problems

Symptoms of vitamin deficiency anemia overlap with those of B-12 and folate deficiencies, also causing additional symptoms:

- fatigue
- muscle weakness and unsteady movements
- pale or yellowish skin
- personality changes

- shortness of breath or dizziness
- irregular heartbeat
- numbness or tingling in hands and feet
- mental confusion or forgetfulness
- weight loss

Many factors contribute to high homocysteine levels. If you have a folate or B vitamin deficiency, you may develop hyperhomocysteinemia.

Other risk factors include:

- low thyroid hormone levels
- psoriasis
- kidney disease
- certain medications
- genetics

If you test positive for elevated homocysteine levels, you could be at an increased risk of developing a number of health issues. Some common conditions associated with high homocysteine are:

- osteoporosis, or bone thinning
- atherosclerosis, or a buildup of fats and other substances in the arterial walls
- thrombosis, a blood vessel blood clot
- venous thrombosis, a blood clot in the veins
- heart attack
- coronary artery disease
- stroke
- dementia
- Alzheimer's disease

All in all, high homocysteine levels in the blood can damage the lining of the arteries. High levels may also make the blood clot more easily than it should. This can increase the risk of blood vessel blockages. A clot inside your blood vessel is called a thrombus. A thrombus can travel in the bloodstream

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